

Metadata

Neilson BJ, Wall CB, Mancini FT, Gewecke CA. (2018) Herbivore biocontrol and manual removal successfully reduce invasive macroalgae on coral reefs. *PeerJ Preprints* 6:e26796v1 <https://doi.org/10.7287/peerj.preprints.26796v1>

Files uploaded to Zenodo follow a directory of ~Desktop/DLNR Invasive Algae. Within the folder 'DLNR Invasive Algae' is the R.markdown script and the html output for the script. Additionally, there is a folder named 'data' that has the following files:

Figure 1_KBaymap.png
Figure 2_AlgaeTypes.png
Figure 3_Treatment.png
InvAlgProjdata_DLNR

Files 1 – 3 go are referenced by the R-markdown script. They are used in the manuscript as Figure 1 – 3. File 'InvAlgProjdata_DLNR' is all the compiled data for the project as a csv file.

InvAlgProjdata_DLNR
column names for *InvAlgProjdata_DLNR*

Factors----

Date: date of assessment in mm/dd/yy
Reef: reef ID number (16, 26, 27, 28)
Treatment: control (no removal of algae and no urchin outplanted), or Treatment
Habitat: aggregate (Ag), pavement (Pave), or mixture of aggregate and pavement (Mix)
Transect: this is the ID for each transect
Time: sampling points (see manuscript for details)
Season: summer or winter, this is the binned time of year assessments took place

**Responses----*

Abiotic: sand/bare substrate/turf (SBT)
As: *Acanthophora spicifera*
CCA: crustose coralline algae
Coral: living reef corals
Ed: *Eucheuma* clade E
Ks: *Kappaphycus* clade A and B
Gs: *Gracilaria salicornia*
NatAlgae: native macroalgae
Other: any other substrate type
Inv_Algae: *Eucheuma* clade E and *Kappaphycus* clade A and B

* all response values represent proportion of cover in each transect, in the R code they are multiplied by 100 to percent